

ADAPTIVE MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMIZATION OF EV CHARGING DECISIONS USING XGBOOST AND TOPSIS

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Abstract: *The paper presents user-specific multi-criteria analysis integrating predictive machine learning to develop a decision-making framework for electric vehicle charging optimization. The framework utilizes an XGBoost model trained on both synthetic and real-world data to predict optimal charger selections across various station-time combinations, with the goal of minimizing charging duration. Three user profiles — time-sensitive, price-sensitive, and speed-sensitive — are incorporated into a TOPSIS-based optimization, which utilizes predictions and includes charging price and speed. The results show that varying user types have significantly different preference for choices: each time-sensitive user chooses fast chargers day / time, each price-sensitive user chooses standard but less expensive chargers, and speed-sensitive users select chargers that provide the highest power charging rate independent of wait time and price. The limitations of static optimization are demonstrated, as well as value of a custom and adaptable approach. The model achieves high prediction accuracy and provides intelligent, user-centric recommendations regarding electric vehicle charging options.*

Keywords: XGBoost, TOPSIS, Multi-criteria decision making, EV charging.

1. INTRODUCTION

The accelerating transition toward electric vehicles (EVs) has created needs for intelligent, personalized, and adaptive EV charging systems. With the growth in charging infrastructure, considerations of user heterogeneity pose an increasing challenge to classical recommendation-based models that have considered static parameters such as location or price. Traditional methods often overlook dynamic user preferences, resulting in low user satisfaction (Habbal & Alrifaie, 2024; Lee et al., 2025). Hence, there is a growing need for decision-making that can predict user's needs and adapt according to user specification.

Artificial intelligence (AI) evolution and the multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) paradigm are seen as promising for improving efficiency in EV charging. For instance, Habbal and Alrifaie (2024) noted that TOPSIS-AHP greatly improves recommendation reliability when compared to heuristics considering price or distance only. Zuo et al. (2023) pointed out the importance of multidimensional profile of users and offered an optimization approach that includes collaborative filtering that aim to balance cost, time and energy. In parallel, there is a growing body of research that applies machine learning techniques to forecast dynamic patterns of demand. For example, Shern et al. (2024) compared efficiency of several prediction models and found out that XGBoost is the one that most persistently outperform other in decreasing forecasting errors. Mahato et al. (2023) introduced a hybrid Jaya–Multi-Verse Optimizer to minimize charging costs and maximize scheduling efficiency.

Increasing demand for flexible decision-making is also evident from recent research on EV route planning. Relying on real-world data, Velimirović et al. (2023a) introduced hybrid methods based on AHP and dynamic programming that allow each EV user to schedule charging stations and routes based on predefined values such as travel time, charging duration, and location attractiveness. Building upon this, Velimirović et al. (2023b) further extended their approach by proposing a hybrid algorithm combining dynamic programming with heuristic components to solve the Electric Vehicle Routing Problem (EVRP). Their model not only balances user needs with travel and charging constraints but also incorporates route optimization under real-

world constraints, demonstrating the importance of personalized and adaptive planning in EV mobility scenarios. Similar study for planning routing and infrastructure includes the main personal limitations on space, behavior, and networks applying hybrid p -median – AHP approach (Janjić et al., 2021).

Two investigations carried out by Ou et al. (2024) and Feng et al. (2025) additionally support the advantages of hybrid models. Studies presented agent systems based on a large language model for understanding user language and consequently for proposing an optimal decision. These researches explain the recent incline toward user-friendly optimization systems, with real-time data-driven information being essential for decision support systems in an EV charging infrastructure.

This study proposes a hybrid framework that integrates predictive machine learning with MCDM to support adaptive, user-specific EV charging decisions. Unlike prior approaches that treat prediction and optimization separately, our model combines both, using three user profiles to generate dynamic, personalized charger-time recommendations.

2. METHODOLOGY

Extreme Gradient Boosting - XGBoost - is a significant component of our methodology and allows us to predict how EV users will use an EV charging station, particularly the predicted duration of each charging session. XGBoost works based on gradient-boosted decision trees (Mustapha & Saeed, 2016; Xia et al., 2017), which is a type of ensemble learning method that captures complex, and relatively unknown non-linear relationships and interactions among some variables. In our case, variables refer to the type of station, time of day, prior congestion level, and trends in user behavior. A substantial element in our optimization methodology is the estimated charging time at each option, which feeds into our multi-criteria weighted ranking. Ultimately, XGBoost will provide an improved input data for the TOPSIS algorithm, which will improve realism and personalization of the optimization process in consideration of actual feedback from the user and station interactions that shape frequent user behavior.

The set of functions f_i in the regression tree model can be learned by minimizing the objective function (Chen et al., 2019):

$$Obj^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[g_i f_i(x_i) + \frac{1}{2} h_i f_i(x_i)^2 \right] + \gamma T + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{j=1}^T w_j^2 = \sum_{j=1}^T \left[\left(\sum_{i \in I_j} g_i \right) w_j + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i \in I_j} h_i + \lambda \right) w_j^2 \right] + \gamma T \quad (1)$$

where $I_j = \{i | q(x_i) = j\}$ indicates the instance set of leaf j , while the gain formula is described in detail in (Chen et al., 2019).

The proposed model merges TOPSIS decision-making with predictive data modeling using the XGBoost algorithm. To produce predictions based on how long users will stay at each station throughout the day, we utilize historical data from a four-station charging facility, which has two fast and two standard stations.

2.1. Formation of Charging Alternatives Based on Station-Time Slot Combinations

In order to construct an authentic and thorough decision space for EV users, we capture both the spatial (charging station) and temporal (time of charging) aspects by defining a discrete choice set of 16 options. This is accomplished through the combination of four stations — two fast-charge (S1_Fast and S2_Fast) and two standard-charge (S3_Stand and S4_Stand) — together with four time intervals (08:00–11:00, 11:00–14:00, 14:00–17:00, and 17:00–20:00). Any given combination of station and time frame represents a plausible charging alternative, forming the basis of the user’s decision problem: “When and where should I charge my vehicle?” Each of these options is evaluated across three quantitative criteria. First, expected user time at the station — including both waiting and charging duration — is predicted using a trained XGBoost regression model based on historical user data, which reflects temporal patterns such as day-of-week, seasonal variation, and typical user behavior. Second, charging cost per kWh varies by charger type and time of day, reflecting dynamic pricing mechanisms that are especially sensitive to peak demand periods (e.g., 11:00–17:00). Third, power output differs by station type, with standard chargers providing 22 kW and fast chargers offering 50 kW, directly impacting the effective charging speed and user satisfaction.

To formalize the decision process, we apply the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). Here, the three criteria are classified as either cost criteria (duration and cost) or benefit criteria (speed). The resulting decision matrix is normalized and weighted according to user-specific preferences. We define three representative user profiles: (1) time-sensitive users, who prioritize minimizing wait and charge duration (weights: [0.6, 0.2, 0.2]); (2) price-sensitive users, who focus on minimizing cost

(weights: [0.2, 0.6, 0.2]); and (3) speed-sensitive users, who prioritize maximum charging power regardless of time or cost (weights: [0.2, 0.2, 0.6]). Each user case is processed separately through the TOPSIS method to generate a ranked ordering of the 16 available charging options.

A context-sensitive decision process involves selecting both a charging station and time slot, reflecting dynamic pricing and congestion. This setup enables the use of MCDM techniques like TOPSIS and supports adaptive optimization based on user preferences.

2.2. Construction of the Decision Matrix for TOPSIS Evaluation

After defining the set of 16 alternatives through combinations of charging stations and time intervals, we develop a decision matrix suitable for multi-criteria decision making. The three evaluation criteria established previously will quantify each alternative: 1. Cost criteria is anticipated duration (minutes); 2. Cost criteria is charging price (€/kWh); 3. Benefit criteria of charging power output (kW).

These three criteria are used to populate a decision matrix $D \in \mathbb{R}^{16 \times 3}$, where each row corresponds to a unique charging alternative (station \times time slot), and each column represents one evaluation criterion. Formally, the matrix D is defined as:

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & d_{13} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} & d_{23} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ d_{161} & d_{162} & d_{163} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where:

- d_{i1} : predicted duration for alternative i ,
- d_{i2} : charging price for alternative i ,
- d_{i3} : power output for alternative i .

Since the criteria are measured in different units (minutes, €/kWh, kW), min-max normalization is applied to scale all values to the [0,1] range. For cost-type criteria (duration and price), values are inverted after normalization so that higher values consistently indicate better options, aligning all criteria under a “higher is better” interpretation. After normalization, a weight vector $w = [w_1, w_2, w_3]$ is applied to reflect the user's preferences for each criterion: w_1 = weight assigned to predicted duration, w_2 = weight assigned to charging price, and w_3 = weight assigned to charging speed.

The set of weight vectors will simulate varying user profiles, as described in the adaptive TOPSIS assessment in the next section. The constructed and normalized matrix will be the input to the TOPSIS algorithm; ranking the alternatives based on their similarity to the ideal dataset and their distance from the worst-case data set allows for multi-criteria recommendation systems that are flexible and sensitive to user strategies and priorities.

2.3. Application of the TOPSIS Method for Multi-Criteria Ranking

To find the best charging option based on user preferences, we use the TOPSIS method, a commonly applied multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) method (Yoon & Hwang, 1981; Shanian & Savadogo, 2006; Siregar, 2019). TOPSIS ranks alternatives based on their relative distance to the ideal solution, valuing both benefit-type and cost-type criteria.

To portray realistic and contextual decision-making behavior we consider a typical EV user who will employ three decision strategies associated with dynamic user preferences. Rather than consider static priorities, our user will evaluate charging station alternatives from three unique vantages: charging station options that minimize total charging time, minimize the costs to charge the EV, and maximize the chargers speed to charge the EV. Each user profile is defined by a specific weight vector across the three criteria, generating a unique preference-based ranking. Time-sensitive users seek to minimize total charging time, so they input a high weight of 0.6 for duration, and low weights of 0.2 for price and charger speed. Price-sensitive users seek to minimize total cost, so they put their greatest weight (0.6) on charging price and only a weight of 0.2 on both duration and speed. Speed-sensitive users are looking for the highest power output regardless of cost or wait time and mean to transfer as much energy as possible to the battery as fast as possible, so they weight charger speed at 0.6 and duration and price both at 0.2.

This way of creating rankings allows analysis of the optimal station-time-slot options vary depending on the user's current preferred profile. The adaptive rankings that we generate from our TOPSIS method, based on each weight assumption, provide the user with a ranking, and an understanding of how those rankings vary based on changing decision contexts caused by trading off the different alternative combinations.

Each user profile generates a distinct TOPSIS ranking of the 16 station-time alternatives, reflecting personalized trade-offs between duration, cost, and charging speed. This enables adaptive recommendations tailored to individual user priorities. The framework supports flexible, real-time decision-making in dynamic environments. Detailed numerical results, including scores and ranked options for each profile, are presented in the following section.

3. NUMERIC RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dataset in this study was real-world data from a real-world application, including 3.395 records of EV charging sessions from 85 users of 105 charging stations at 25 sites (Asensio et al., 2020). The real-world dataset initially included 24 attributes, including time-related session attributes, energy attributes, user IDs, and station attributes. A thorough feature selection process was completed in order to narrow the criterion variables for model relevance and interpretability which resulted in selected times, charging duration, user ID, user and station IDs, and location indicators. Additional features were engineered to provide better review of charging performance such as total energy delivered, cost estimates based on dynamic pricing, and congestion measures by utilizing historical data. The synthetic dataset replicates user–station interactions from the original data and simulates time-based behavior over a full quarter. The variety of the full dataset with the modeling capability of XGBoost developed robust prediction of user duration at charging alternatives, this predicted duration served as base input for the TOPSIS-based optimization framework.

To assess model performance, the standard regression performance measures were employed: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Coefficient of Determination (R^2), based on a strong 5-fold cross validation (generalizability and reduced risk of overfitting).

The XGBoost model represented the greatest performance at $MAE = 2.15$, $RMSE = 2.83$, and $R^2 = 0.85$, reflecting an improvement of up to 16% in RMSE, and greater than 20% in MAE over Decision Tree and Random Forest models, underscoring its strength and efficacy in accurately modeling EV charging durations.

Figure 1 indicates a strong linear relationship in the predicted versus observed congestion values along the diagonal, also showing that the bias is approximately equal over the range of values.

Along with regression-based validation, we also evaluated the model's top-1 user-level decision accuracy in selected time slots during the day. We found that the model accurately predicted the preferred charging option for 76.1% of users at 08-11h, 78.0% at 11-14h, 74.2 at 14-17h, and 75.8% at 17-20h. These values present evidence of the operational validity of the model, particularly where predictive as it behaved correctly at applicable times for charging owing to the mid-day decision opportunity. This consistency supports its use as a real-time decision support tool.

Adaptive TOPSIS results show that optimal charging decisions vary significantly by user profile (Table 1). When the model prefers shorter charging durations (time-sensitive users), fast chargers in time slots of lower congestion such as midday (11-14h) are soon viable options. However, we still find some standard stations in the top one or two choices, if they have particularly low predicted waiting times. This indicates that users with the time constraint may sometimes place convenience ahead of the speed of charging.

Figure 1: XGBoost: True vs. Predicted Value of Congestion

Alternative choices change dramatically for users who are price sensitive. The highest ranked charging options are almost all standard stations with the lowest cost rates. While standard stations typically lead to

longer charge times, users willing to put up with the time trade-off in order to save costs will tend to select such options.

Table 1: TOPSIS Rankings of Charging Alternatives by User Profile

Alternative	Duration	Price	Speed	TOPSIS TimeSensitive	Rank	TOPSIS PriceSensitive	Rank	TOPSIS SpeedSensitive	Rank
S2_Fast_2	25.804	0.4	50	0.759747	1	0.320377	13	0.759747	3
S1_Fast_2	29.472	0.4	50	0.754812	2	0.31753	14	0.759212	4
S4_Stand_2	28.702	0.3	22	0.726891	3	0.498401	9	0.265536	9
S4_Stand_1	138.99	0.2	22	0.306195	11	0.700567	1	0.246901	11
S3_Stand_1	146.63	0.2	22	0.28106	13	0.694707	2	0.244404	12
S3_Stand_4	151.73	0.2	22	0.266949	15	0.690766	3	0.243005	13
S1_Fast_1	139.95	0.3	50	0.334073	9	0.515048	5	0.761372	1
S2_Fast_4	141.01	0.3	50	0.330328	10	0.514415	6	0.76012	2
S2_Fast_2	25.804	0.4	50	0.759747	1	0.320377	13	0.759747	3

The TOPSIS scores illustrate this shift in alternatives by penalizing higher price stations irrespective of charging speed. Thus alternatives that would be nearly eliminated in cost- or time-based analyses emerge as highest recommendations in price-based optimization scenarios.

On the other hand, speed-sensitive users exhibit a strong and consistent preference over charging with high-power fast chargers over options linked with longer predicted times, even at moderate cost. For speed-sensitive users, the technical capability of a 50 kW station is better than the potential wait times and costs. While alternatives in terms of early morning or late afternoon on fast stations are still top scores, their success reflects the relationship between technical capability and user intentions that change time related to cost.

One key insight from the three profiles is the variation in rankings. The same alternative can be in the lead in one context, and not lead a few months later. For example, a fast station in a low-congestion time slot, may rank first for a time-sensitive user, but when price dominates the decision then it can fall considerably down the ranking. This illustrates the need to update the decision-making framework to represent personal priorities rather than to adopt an optimal solution for all.

In addition to the analysis of preferences across the subgroups of profiles, the outcomes provide another useful perspective to develop our understanding of temporal patterns. The time slots selected by some profiles, in particular, time slots such as 11-14h are characteristics preferred by several profiles, which may indicate an architecture style (station load and price structure) that may be helpful when planning infrastructure. For instance, there were time slots that were selected at very low rates (e.g., 17-20h) that were frequently shown as the lowest preferred alternatives, providing support for sending congestion-aware decisions.

The model effectively captures interactions between user type, station type, and time of day—crucial for developing intelligent EV guidance systems. These systems can adapt based on user behavior, enabling highly personalized charging plans. Unlike static methods, this approach supports real-time, data-driven recommendations aligned with individual preferences. Overall, the findings highlight the need for user-centric, preference-aware optimization in EV infrastructure. Combining machine learning with adaptive MCDM methods like TOPSIS enables personalized navigation and energy management, reflecting user-specific trade-offs beyond technical parameters alone.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a hybrid framework that integrates XGBoost predictions with TOPSIS-based multi-criteria optimization to generate personalized EV charging recommendations. By modeling three user profiles, the approach adjusts to individual preferences and system conditions, and performs better than static decision methods. Results show high predictive accuracy and effective preference-based differentiation which supports the use of real-time, user-focused guidance in smart EV infrastructure.

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LITERATURE

- Asensio, O. I., Apablaza, C. Z., Lawson, M., & Walsh, S. E. (2020). Replication data for: A field experiment on workplace norms and electric vehicle charging etiquette. Tech. Rep., doi:10.7910/DVN/NFPQLW
- Chen, M., Liu, Q., Chen, S., Liu, Y., Zhang, C. H., & Liu, R. (2019). XGBoost-based algorithm interpretation and application on post-fault transient stability status prediction of power system. *IEEE Access*, 7, 13149-13158.
- Feng, J., Cui, C., Zhang, C., & Fan, Z. (2025). Large Language Model Based Agent Framework for Electric Vehicle Charging Behavior Simulation. In T.T., Lie, C., Shen, G., Li & Y., Liu. (Eds.), *2025 10th Asia Conference on Power and Electrical Engineering (ACPEE)*, (pp. 2683–2687). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACPEE64358.2025.11040586>
- Habbal, A., & Alrifai, M. F. (2024). A User-Preference-Based Charging Station Recommendation for Electric Vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 25(9), 11617–11634. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2024.3379469>
- Janjić, A., Velimirović, L., Velimirović, J., & Vranić, P. (2021). Estimating the optimal number and locations of electric vehicle charging stations: the application of multi-criteria p-median methodology. *Transportation Planning and Technology*, 44(8), 827–842. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03081060.2021.1992177>
- Lee, D., Kim, D. S., Chung, B. J., & Chung, Y. M. (2025). Recommendation of Electric Vehicle Charging Stations in Driving Situations Based on a Preference Objective Function. *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, 16(4), 192. <https://doi.org/10.3390/wevj16040192>
- Mahato, D., Aharwal, V. K., & Sinha, A. (2023). Multi-objective optimisation model and hybrid optimization algorithm for Electric Vehicle Charge Scheduling. *Journal of Experimental & Theoretical Artificial Intelligence*, 36(8), 1645–1667. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0952813X.2023.2165719>
- Mustapha, I. B., & Saeed, F. (2016). Bioactive molecule prediction using extreme gradient boosting. *Molecules*, 21(8), 983. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules21080983>
- Ou, P., Wang, Y., Lin, W., & Wu, J. (2024). An LLM-Based Modeling and Decision Optimization for User-Centric Electric Vehicle Charging. 2024 IEEE 8th Conference on Energy Internet and Energy System Integration (EI2), 4078–4083. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EI264398.2024.10991378>
- Shanian, A., & Savadogo, O. (2006). TOPSIS multiple-criteria decision support analysis for material selection of metallic bipolar plates for polymer electrolyte fuel cell. *Journal of Power Sources*, 159(2), 1095–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2005.12.092>
- Shern, S. J., Sarker, M. T., Haram, M. H. S. M., Ramasamy, G., Thiagarajah, S. P., & Al Farid, F. (2024). Artificial Intelligence Optimization for User Prediction and Efficient Energy Distribution in Electric Vehicle Smart Charging Systems. *Energies*, 17(22), 5772. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17225772>
- Siregar, I. (2019, December). Supplier selection by using analytical hierarchy process (ahp) and techniques for order preference methods with similarities to ideal solutions (topsis). In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1339, No. 1, p. 012023). IOP Publishing. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1339/1/012023
- Velimirović, L. Z., Janjić, A., Vranić, P., Velimirović, J. D., & Petkovski, I. (2023a). Determining the Optimal Route of Electric Vehicle Using a Hybrid Algorithm Based on Fuzzy Dynamic Programming. *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, 31(2), 609–618. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TFUZZ.2022.3205045>
- Velimirović, L. Z., Janjić, A., Vranić, P., Petkovski, I., & Velimirović, J. D. (2023b, November). Solving Electric Vehicle Routing Problem Using Hybrid Algorithm Based on Dynamic Programming. In *2023 31st Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TELFOR59449.2023.10372746>
- Xia, Y., Liu, C., Li, Y., & Liu, N. (2017). A boosted decision tree approach using Bayesian hyper-parameter optimization for credit scoring. *Expert systems with applications*, 78, 225-241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2017.02.017>
- Yoon, K., & Hwang, C. L. (1981). TOPSIS (technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution)—a multiple attribute decision making, w: Multiple attribute decision making—methods and applications, a state-of-the-at survey. *Berlin: Springer Verlag*, 128, 140. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-48318-9>
- Zuo, X., Bi, J., Wang, Y., & Du, Y. (2023). A Charging Guidance Optimization Model for Electric Vehicle Travel by Considering Multi-Dimensional Preferences of Users. *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, 14(7), 171. <https://doi.org/10.3390/wevj14070171>